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“I NEED SOMEONE TOO”

I set aside the tears
I set aside the pain

I have to walk a mile
And another mile with a smile

I live and breathe the affliction
And still need to be in strong condition

Crying is not an option
But it kills me like potion

No one ask if I'm fine,
Because they see me, always divine

But look, please look beyond my smiles,
See the cresses of my eyes.

Watch me slowly despair,
Life has been unfair.

You put too much pressure on my shoulder,
Because you think I could carry the boulder.

But you have overlooked my heart,
How weary and hurt.

I look at you and longed,
That perhaps think that I'm not that strong.
Notice that, I need someone too.
Oh, I need embraces too.

I too delight to unload the worry,
That is coupled with depression and anxiety.

Notice that, I need someone too.

Oh, I need a tap on the shoulder too.

I too want to savor the pleasure,
Of being helped with joy.

Oh, I need someone too.
Because the strong gets weary too.

